

Adsorption Indicator in the Volumetric Estimation of Sulphates. A Colloido-chemical Study.

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Wellings has pointed out in a paper (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28,561) the applicability of fluorescein (evidently sodium fluoresceinate) as an adsorption indicator in the volumetric estimation of soluble sulphates. He has offered a tentative explanation for the colour changes which the precipitate at the end-point undergoes, when magnesium or manganese sulphate solution is titrated against barium hydroxide using the adsorption indicator. It is clear from the 'probable' explanation offered by him in the above mentioned paper that the mechanism of the reactions at the interface has not been fully elucidated. "The anions of the fluorescein are not adsorbed by the colloidal particles of the metallic hydroxide so long as the sulphate ions are present in excess. When, however, the sulphate ions are removed as barium sulphate, the fluorescein anions are then adsorbed and change colour as soon as barium ions are also adsorbed. The colour change is, therefore, visible when there is a drop of barium hydroxide solution in excess." The object of the present communication is to elucidate the exact mechanism of the changes taking place in the system. The phenomena connected with the colour changes in the system, the influence of p_H changes in the reaction mixture, and of the ion environment during the course of the titration, have also been elucidated from the colloido-chemical standpoint.

In order to show that the magnesium hydroxide and not the barium sulphate gives rise to the colour change at the end-point of the titration, the following experiments were tried. In a stoppered bottle containing magnesium hydroxide, freshly precipitated from magnesium sulphate and sodium hydroxide solution (the precipitate being thoroughly washed free from soluble sulphate), a few drops of sodium fluoresceinate were added and shaken up with water. After allowing to stand, the precipitate was coloured pink, showing the same colour as

that obtained in the titration of magnesium sulphate against barium hydroxide. The colour change was marked in the case where the magnesium hydroxide was precipitated with a slight excess of magnesium salt; and not so well where a slight excess of alkali was used for the preparation.

The colour changes with fluoresceinate as indicator, take place when solutions of manganese or magnesium sulphates are titrated against barium hydroxide and do not take place in the titration of other soluble sulphates. From the table of the precipitation of p_H of the hydroxides of metals (Britton, "Hydrogen Ions," 1932, p. 325) it is found that for Mg it is 10.5, and for Mn, 8.5—8.8, while for other metals such as Cu, Al, Fe, Zn, etc., the precipitation p_H is in the acid range. Thus the success of the experiment using Mg and Mn sulphates can be attributed to the precipitation p_H of these hydroxides being in the distinctly alkaline range. The p_H at the equivalence point should be in the alkaline range in order that there may be a sufficient concentration of fluoresceinate ions which can be adsorbed. The adsorption of fluoresceinate ions by the surface will depend upon other factors such as the electrical charge of the surface, as also the presence or otherwise of other strongly adsorbable ions namely the hydrogen and hydroxyl ions or the constituent ions of the solid phase (cf. Mukherjee and Iyer, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 307). The above considerations can easily explain why the colour change does not take place when aluminium sulphate is titrated against barium hydroxide. It is seen that since the precipitation p_H of aluminium hydroxide is in the neighbourhood of 4.0, the precipitate can adsorb on its surface either hydrogen ions or aluminium ions or both, when the p_H corresponds to this value.

The process of adsorption taking place on the surface of magnesium hydroxide particles, when magnesium sulphate is being titrated against barium hydroxide, may be pictured as follows. The precipitate during the initial stage of the titration and until the end-point is reached adsorbs 'primarily' on its surface a layer of magnesium ions, since this is the constituent ion of the solid phase; the mobile sheet of the double layer consisting of sulphate or hydroxyl ions. The 'electrical' adsorption of fluoresceinate ions in the 'mobile' layer, or the 'deforming' influence by the primarily adsorbed magnesium ions on the fluoresceinate ions will depend upon the nature and concentration of other ions in solution which are likely to be adsorbed by the hydroxide. The colour change taking place on the

precipitate is due to this 'deforming' influence on the dyestuff anions as has been pointed out by Fajans (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1923, 29, 495 ; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 137, 221).

The above considerations are illustrated by the following experiments. A series of bottles containing the same volume (10 c.c.) of 0.1N-magnesium sulphate solution were shaken up with 5 drops of sodium fluoresceinate solution (0.5 % strong) with varying volumes of barium hydroxide (0.1 N) in the neighbourhood of the equivalence point *viz.*, 9.5 c.c. to 10.5 c.c. On allowing the precipitates to settle for the same period (about 5 minutes) it was observed that there was the maximum intensity of pink colour in the precipitate when the solutions were mixed up in exactly equivalent proportions. The supernatant liquid in this case was practically colourless. On either side of the equivalence point the intensity of the yellow colour of the supernatant liquid (due to sodium fluoresceinate) goes on increasing. The colour change of the precipitate is not anything so sharp as stated by Wellings. The equivalence point can be rather judged better by the intensity of the yellow colour of the solution after allowing the precipitate to settle, though this is rather tedious in routine titrations on account of the time taken by the precipitate to settle down. That the colour change of the precipitate is a gradual process is to be expected from the general principles relating to the adsorption by a precipitate in an environment consisting of ions of varying concentration and adsorbability. Beyond the equivalence point of the titration, the precipitate of magnesium hydroxide is in contact with a solution whose p_H is higher than 10.5 (the precipitation p_H of magnesium hydroxide) and as such shows strong preferential adsorption for hydroxyl ions. A distinct change in the colour of the precipitate from pink to light orange, is therefore, noticed owing to the desorption of the fluoresceinate ions.

Another interesting observation made during the course of these experiments is that when the precipitate, at the equivalence point, which is coloured pink, is kept in contact with the titrated solution for a few hours (not more than 24 hours), a gradual fading in the colour of the precipitate takes place, while the yellow colour of the solution deepens. This shows that the effect of 'ageing' of the magnesium hydroxide particles, brings about a growth in size of the particles with a desorption of the 'primarily' adsorbed magnesium ions, and a corresponding number of fluoresceinate ions in the 'mobile' layer. A feeble pink colour of the precipitate persists whatever be the length

of time for which it is kept, thus showing that the primarily adsorbed magnesium ions are responsible for the colour changes. Since the colour change is thus essentially due to the 'electrical' adsorption (according to Mukherjee's theory, *loc. cit.*) of the fluoresceinate ions by the magnesium hydroxide, the effect of neutral salts like potassium chloride, potassium nitrate on the course of the titration has also been investigated. As Wellings has stated, the end-point is affected by the presence of these salts, though it has not been possible to make quantitative measurements of the change in the 'end-point' due to the presence of these salts. The end-point of the titration becomes very indistinct, because the simultaneous 'electrical' adsorption of the anions of the neutral salt as also of the fluoresceinate ions becomes possible, the relative amounts so adsorbed being governed by their respective concentrations and adsorbabilities. Hence the colour change of the precipitate becomes indistinct. Hydroxyl ions, however, have a sharp effect on the end-point, on account of their strong adsorption by the surface of magnesium hydroxide.

SUMMARY.

1. The work of Wellings on the titration of magnesium and manganese sulphates against barium hydroxide using fluorescein as adsorption indicator has been extended. The influence of the p_H of the solution and the ion environment has been pointed out.

2. The results have been explained on the basis of the 'chemical' and 'electrical' adsorption of ions by particles as put forward by Mukherjee, combined with theory of 'deformation' of ions at interfaces enunciated by Fajans.

My best thanks are due to Prof. B. Sanjiva Rao, M.A., Ph.D., for his kind interest in the work, and to Prof. J. N. Mukherjee for his kind criticism of the paper.

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Received December 21, 1934.